

Adaptation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to Improve Knowledge Management (KM) in Academic Libraries

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17209413>

Abstract

Purpose: Academic libraries must proactively adapt to artificial intelligence (AI) because AI can lead to positive changes in how libraries operate and serve their users in the digital age. However, careful attention to related issues is necessary for the ethical and successful implementation of AI. This paper explored the potential of artificial intelligence (AI) to improve knowledge management in academic libraries.

Methodology: The paper utilised an extensive literature review, case studies, and practical insights to explore librarians' perspectives on the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) to enhance knowledge management in academic libraries. It examined the role of artificial intelligence in knowledge management, along with AI-driven tools and applications for libraries, and considered ethical and privacy issues. Additionally, the paper discussed challenges related to AI and knowledge management, as well as future trends and research opportunities in AI for libraries.

Findings: While AI offers promising solutions to increase efficiency and effectiveness, the paper identifies several challenges and concerns that need to be addressed, such as unstable power supply, inadequate infrastructure, lack of expertise, financial uncertainty, and user privacy.

Conclusion: The study finds that the emergence of AI to enhance knowledge management represents a milestone for academic libraries. AI ensures that libraries remain relevant in the digital age while also boosting efficiency and personalisation.

Recommendation: Libraries play a vital role in promoting AI adoption by offering education and training to staff, enabling them to use AI tools effectively and confidently. Libraries are also responsible for supporting best practices and encouraging innovative AI applications by fostering an environment that values creativity and information sharing.

Study Type: Descriptive Research

Keywords: Academic libraries, artificial intelligence, knowledge management.

Introduction

As globalisation progresses and technology improves, library professionals, information specialists, and librarians have new roles to assume and new skills to acquire. In the academic library sector, knowledge management is a process that supports organisational development, innovation, and promotes collaboration and teamwork. It is a successful model and strategy that proves to be an all-encompassing solution for libraries in the digital age (Madge, 2017). The traditional methods of information organisation and retrieval in academic libraries are no longer sufficient due to the proliferation of unstructured data, including emails, video transcripts, and conversations across various platforms. Artificial intelligence and machine learning models allow you to collect, organise, and utilise the vast amounts of data within your organisation by automating many of the labour-intensive data management tasks. Typically, knowledge management (KM) involves three essential components: procedures, technology,

and people. The human element is a vital function, accounting for 70% of knowledge management performance, because knowledge is created and shared by humans. Additionally, all practical aspects of knowledge management, including its creation, storage, sharing, and use, are governed by processes, which make up 20% of the total. The third component, technology, enables individuals to carry out these procedures and ensures that information is accessible whenever and wherever it is needed (Thakuri et al., 2024).

Artificial intelligence and knowledge management are closely interconnected. While AI employs machine learning to accelerate knowledge discovery, simplify content curation, and personalise information delivery to enhance knowledge management, knowledge management provides AI algorithms with context, structure, and understanding. This paradigm shift, driven by their convergence, creates new opportunities to increase competitive advantage, productivity, and creativity (Jallow, Renukappa, & Suresh, 2020). Traditionally, library and information workers have been responsible for gathering, processing, sharing, storing, and utilising information to meet the personal and professional needs of library patrons through interdisciplinary services. However, their roles are increasingly expanding beyond information management. The author also highlights the significant impact on knowledge management initiatives involving the identification, gathering, development, resolution, archiving, and exchange of information. Librarians and information specialists should engage in dialogue with external information and knowledge providers and manage their connections with them. Knowledge management has established new ground in the field of library and information science (Mutmule, 2021).

Over 80% of enterprises are expected to have used or developed systems enabled by generative AI by 2026, according to Gartner's 2023 study. This significant increase suggests that businesses are increasingly relying on these advanced AI systems to enhance operational efficiency and foster innovation through effective knowledge management. This trend raises the need to explore how AI can be utilised to improve knowledge management in academic libraries (Gartner, 2023). This paper will examine the role of artificial intelligence in knowledge management, AI-powered tools and applications for academic libraries, ethical and privacy considerations, and successful AI integration in libraries. It will also address challenges associated with AI and knowledge management, as well as future trends, research opportunities in AI for libraries, and provide some recommendations.

Objectives

To examine the role of artificial intelligence in enhancing knowledge management practices in libraries.

1. To identify and evaluate AI tools and applications currently used in libraries
2. To investigate the perceptions of librarians and library users towards the use of AI technologies in enhancing library services.
3. To analyse the challenges and limitations faced by libraries in implementing AI in knowledge management.

The role of artificial intelligence in knowledge management

Integrating artificial intelligence into knowledge management in libraries automates the processes of knowledge capture, retrieval, and synthesis, which may enhance organisational performance (Chen, 2024). AI can be utilised to support the knowledge management (KM) processes that organisations have already implemented (Jallow, Renukappa, & Suresh,

2020). It holds significant potential for improving information service delivery (Echedom & Okuonghae, 2021) and is recognised as a dynamic technology capable of accelerating library services in a positive direction (Jha, 2023). One notable application is the use of chatbots, which serve as powerful AI tools in libraries to boost user satisfaction (Sanji, Behzadi, & Gomroki, 2022). AI enables ChatGPT to advance academia and librarianship in both challenging and exciting ways, thereby generating new scholarly knowledge and educating future professionals (Lund & Wang, 2023). Wheatley & Hervieux (2019) stated that the dominant topic in the technology discourse for years has been the growth of AI and added that AI definitely influences how individuals search for information.

Waykar (2022) highlighted several benefits of integrating AI into knowledge management, including the ability for businesses to automate repetitive and time-consuming procedures, access vast data repositories for insightful information, and support data-driven decision-making. Secondly, organisations, including libraries, can now extract valuable patterns, correlations, and trends from enormous datasets that were previously incomprehensible to humans, thanks to AI-driven knowledge discovery tools. Thirdly, AI-powered knowledge retrieval systems also enable librarians to access relevant information quickly, promoting well-informed decision-making and continuous learning. According to Jarrahi (2023), several opportunities are linked to the implementation of emerging AI-enabled systems for KM, including the potential role of AI in supporting key dimensions of KM—namely, creation, storage and retrieval, sharing, and application of knowledge. This integration yields positive implications for the development and management of AI systems, leveraging the components of people, infrastructure, and processes. AI enables libraries to adapt to the needs of their patrons effectively, transforming operations and services for enhanced patron experiences and organisational success. Libraries can improve their operations, serve their communities more effectively, and maintain their leadership position in the information landscape by adopting these technologies.

AI-driven tools and applications for libraries

According to Abba (2024), problem solving, natural language processing, artificial neural networks, genetic algorithms, expert systems, knowledge engineering, artificial life, deep learning, intelligent control, and other technical fields are currently the most prominent areas of artificial intelligence. Mannheimer (2024) explained that AI implementation is expanding in many academic libraries for digitised and born-digital texts and images, metadata extraction and reference services, electronic theses and dissertations, and maps. Knowledge management transforms the library experience for both users and librarians in terms of professional skills and automation. In library contexts, Cox, A. M., & Mazumdar (2024) emphasised that AI is being applied in two main areas for users: namely, knowledge discovery and chatbots. He further observed that the use of AI in knowledge discovery involves applying AI tools to describe and manage library collections, especially unique archival materials in research libraries, which can also be utilised in legal texts and knowledge within law libraries, particularly when the volume of materials is too large for manual metadata creation.

Beyond simply improving operations, artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to fundamentally reshape academic research and knowledge acquisition. Libraries equipped with AI-powered tools for text mining, natural language processing, and semantic analysis foster deep multidisciplinary collaboration and innovation, ushering in an era of unparalleled knowledge and understanding. Furthermore, AI-enabled predictive analytics are driving a new phase of proactive service delivery and resource planning, enabling libraries to forecast user preferences and needs. The integration of artificial intelligence in libraries is crucial for

developing a dynamic and responsive knowledge ecosystem amidst constant change. By adopting AI-driven technologies, libraries reinforce their role as essential centres for knowledge discovery and dissemination, shaping the future of information services in an increasingly digital world (Bisht et al., 2023). Some academic libraries in Africa have implemented AI technologies such as chatbots, ChatGPT, LibKey, robots, RFID, and Grammarly. These tools support various functions, including responding to user queries, cataloguing, self-checkout, library promotion, statistical analysis, and managing book loans.

Ethical and privacy considerations

Akinagbe (2024) suggests that there are significant privacy and security concerns linked to the use of AI systems, especially regarding data collection and monitoring. Large amounts of personal data are often needed for AI models, raising questions about how this data is processed, stored, and protected. These issues could lead to serious privacy breaches or misuse. Furthermore, while AI-driven surveillance might improve security in certain contexts, it can also infringe on individuals' privacy, resulting in extensive profiling and tracking. According to Magomedov, Mashukov, and Kremleva (2023), there is a threat that this technology might replace librarians' roles, which is viewed as the main reason for its criticism. Many librarians feel threatened by this prospect, believing that AI could surpass human capabilities to such an extent that librarians may become outdated. However, it is clear that more AI-powered tools are being developed every day, and there appears to be no sign of these technologies being restricted or regulated. Mohamed, Ramjani, and Hussain (2024) highlight ethical issues as another important aspect of AI adoption in libraries. Transparency and accountability of AI systems are crucial to maintain user trust. Libraries must ensure the ethical use of AI tools by establishing clear rules and regulations governing their application. Addressing issues such as bias in AI algorithms and ensuring that AI systems are developed and used fairly and impartially is essential. Rajkumar et al. (2024) discussed ethical considerations related to user consent and manipulation, emphasising principles of duty, fairness, and transparency. They noted that digital libraries should adhere to ethical standards and consider the broader societal implications of their data practices. To prevent biases, including racial prejudices, it is vital to ensure inclusivity throughout the consent process. Organisations must recognise that users from diverse backgrounds may have different privacy preferences, and they need to design consent processes that are accessible to all clients.

Successful AI integration in libraries

The study titled "The impact of AI on library information service quality" by Amalia, Kurniawati, & Fahmi (2024) highlights successful AI integration in academic and public libraries across Indonesia. The research reveals a positive acceptance of AI among library professionals, increased user satisfaction, and the potential for more dynamic library services resulting from AI adoption. It helps deepen understanding of AI's implications for libraries and emphasises the importance of responsible AI deployment. According to "Redefining library services: The role of Artificial intelligence and machine learning in modern libraries" by Alam (2025), the research mainly focuses on key AI-based tools, such as chatbots, recommendation systems, and automated cataloguing software, which improve library efficiency and user experience. He states that the successful implementation of AI has significantly enhanced the availability and use of information resources, aiding in the realisation of library goals.

In "Artificial intelligence in libraries" by Omame & Alex-Nmecha (2020), the positive impact of AI in academic libraries is effectively examined across areas such as expert systems for reference services, book reading and shelf-reading robots, virtual reality for immersive

learning, among others. The study emphasised that Artificial Intelligence will significantly enhance library operations and services, increasing the relevance of libraries in an ever-evolving digital society. “Reshaping the library landscape: Exploring the integration of artificial intelligence in libraries” by Jyoti & Kumar (2024) investigated AI integration in libraries by utilising artificially intelligent algorithms, natural language processing, and other innovative technologies to automate processes, improve decision-making, and provide customised assistance. The study highlighted key points such as virtual assistants that can help users navigate the extensive resources available in libraries, making it easier to find relevant information. In addition to the successful application of AI in libraries, these technologies—such as intelligent cataloguing systems—can automate the organisation and categorisation of resources, saving time for library staff and supporting collection development.

Abudulsalami (2024) investigated “artificial intelligence in academic libraries and its impact on library services and operations”. The article explores successful implementation of various AI applications such as virtual assistants, recommendation systems, and data analytics, and assesses their effectiveness in enhancing user experiences and optimising library functions. The article highlights visible benefits of AI such as improved information retrieval, personalised user experiences, automated cataloguing and metadata management, chatbots, and predictive analytics. Cornejo (2024) examined “Navigating the future: integration of AI in school libraries”. Findings revealed that integrating AI in academic libraries personalises content and offers a time-saving feature that aligns with the specific needs of users and the readiness of librarians. The author acknowledges that AI is not a one-size-fits-all solution and suggests that librarians continue to be lifelong learners to incorporate AI into their library services effectively.

“AI in Libraries” by Freeman (2024) offers insights into the evolving role of AI in academic institutions, research facilitation, and information literacy development, reflecting a dynamic landscape of technological innovation within Georgia's libraries. The study found that equipping incoming first-year students with foundational knowledge and resources for the ethical and practical use of AI tools in their coursework helps students develop the necessary skills and understanding to approach AI tools with discernment in an ever-changing technological landscape while adhering to their librarians' restrictions and policies. The study titled “Integrating AI-Powered Library Systems to Enhance Research and Learning in English Language Departments: A Case Study of Faculty and Student Perceptions” by AI Fraidan (2024) presents a successful integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into academic institutions, transforming various aspects of higher education, with academic libraries being one of the key areas experiencing rapid advancement. The study explored the perceptions of faculty and students regarding the use of AI-driven technologies in the library, such as automated research assistants, personalised content recommendations, and AI-based search engines. The findings suggest that while AI improves research efficiency and personalises learning.

According to “The AI-supported Language Library Model: It is Not About the CALL Tools, It is About the Language Library” by Devi & Sharma (2024), the integration of AI technologies is not about standalone tools but about facilitators within a wider ecosystem of language resources and learning methodologies. The study emphasised how redefining AI's role within a dynamic, user-focused language library aims to increase learner engagement, personalise experiences, and improve the overall effectiveness of language acquisition processes. Kapoor, Mahida and John (2024) concentrated on how AI can enhance the research experience by making tools and assistance more accessible to individual users. Findings showed that machine learning techniques, natural language processing (NLP), and user tracking are utilised by this system to provide personalised suggestions based on study topics,

preferences, and previous interactions with users. They found that the system can enhance idea generation and search methods in real-time by responding to how users conduct their research. This reduces search time and makes results more accurate.

Challenges of AI and knowledge management

According to the Emiri (2023) study, the adoption of AI is hindered by several factors, including the significant disruption that AI causes to traditional library services, a lack of expertise, the need for training prior to implementation, as well as unstable power supplies and inadequate infrastructure. According to Tait & Pierson (2022), a lack of expertise and the requirement for training may impede the adoption of AI and robotics in libraries. Adjeo & Misau (2021) examined the potential applications of artificial intelligence in academic libraries in Nigeria. Machado et al. (2024) argue that challenges such as ethical considerations and resource constraints emerge as a result of AI. The study by Ajakaye (2022) reported that AI challenges include financial uncertainty, openness to change, technical know-how, slow learning curves among library staff, users' privacy, linguistic capabilities, and understanding users' emotions. Amalia, Kurniawati & Fahmi (2024) suggest that challenges such as staff training and data privacy issues exist in integrating AI into academic libraries. Alam (2025) highlights significant challenges in adopting AI in academic libraries, including data privacy concerns, the need for specialised training, and the potential for job displacement.

Conclusion

AI ensures that libraries remain relevant in the digital age while enhancing efficiency and personalisation. Despite these advancements, libraries must address issues such as algorithmic bias, data protection, and staff training to ensure the ethical and proper use of AI in library operations. The development of AI to improve knowledge management marks a significant milestone for academic libraries. Integrating AI into knowledge management signifies a shift in how academic libraries protect user trust and data privacy. As libraries increasingly rely on AI for operational efficiency and informed decision-making through knowledge management, they encounter challenges while navigating the complexities of AI. Academic libraries need to proactively adopt AI, as it can bring about positive changes in how they operate and serve users in the digital era. However, careful attention to related issues is crucial for the ethical implementation of AI. AI is transforming academic libraries by enabling data-driven decisions, personalising user experiences, and boosting efficiency. Nonetheless, there are numerous obstacles associated with using open-source AI, including resource limitations, technical complexity, and moral considerations. Addressing these requires careful planning, dedicated effort, instruction, and a commitment to ethical standards. The evolving landscape of artificial intelligence in libraries demands that librarians actively guide the technology's use to align with core principles of accessibility, diversity, and user-centred service.

Recommendations

Integrating AI in knowledge management in academic libraries can enhance the effectiveness and output. Here are some recommendations:

Libraries should incorporate AI technologies that support essential knowledge management activities, such as creation, storage, retrieval, and sharing, to enhance service efficiency and informed decision-making. This involves deploying AI tools that automate routine tasks and aid in the strategic utilisation of knowledge.

Libraries should adopt and regularly assess AI tools such as chatbots, recommendation systems, and automated cataloguing software to ensure they meet user needs and enhance access and user experience. Selection should be based on functionality, ease of use, and alignment with library objectives.

Library management should regularly hold feedback and engagement sessions with staff and users to understand their views, address concerns, and promote acceptance of AI tools. This will build trust, encourage collaboration, and keep AI tools user-focused.

Libraries should develop strategic plans to address implementation barriers such as lack of technical expertise, ethical concerns, and infrastructure deficits. This involves investing in staff training, strengthening the IT infrastructure, and establishing ethical guidelines for the use of AI in knowledge management.

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